

DESIRA: Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas

Data Management Plan

30 November 2019

desira

Data Management Plan

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1. Introduction

The Open Research Data Pilot of the European Commission enables open access and reuse of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects. There are two main pillars to the Pilot: developing a Data Management Plan (DMP) and providing open access to research data.

In order to adhere to the Pilot, research consortia under H2020 have to:

- Develop (and keep up-to-date) a Data Management Plan (DMP).
- Deposit data in a research data repository.
- Ensure third parties can freely access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate your data.
- Provide related information and identify (or provide) the tools needed to use the raw data to validate the research.

The Pilot applies to:

- The data (and metadata) needed to validate results in scientific publications.
- Other curated and/or raw data (and metadata)

The DMP will function as a guiding document to ensure good data management throughout the lifecycle of the project in order to make the information collected and produced Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR).

2. Scope

This DMP describes how research data are managed both throughout the lifecycle of DESIRA and after the end of the project. It identifies procedures and minimum requirements to collect, store, analysed, and publish data in a consistent way according to the FAIR principles.

This document is a living document and will be regularly updated when necessary. All project partners will be informed of the changes made to this document. Common standards, folder structure and identifiers will be agreed in the Project Steering Group (PSG) meetings, and made available via the internal information processes (minutes) and during the meeting of the next General Assembly (GA).

3. Data Summary

3.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

DESIRA will carry out a participatory Socio-Economic Impact Assessment of digitisation through a multi-actor approach and a multi-disciplinary community connecting Academia, Research Organizations, SMEs, Private for Profit, NGOs, Development Agencies, Public Authorities, Citizen groups/local Communities and Media from 15 different European countries.

The overarching goal of DESIRA is to improve the capacity of society and of political bodies to respond to the challenges that digitisation generates in rural areas, agriculture and forestry in the next ten years. To achieve this goal, we want to build a knowledge and methodological base that increases the capacity of a wide range of actors to assess past, current and future socio-economic impact – including gender differences - of ICT-related innovation, to embody Responsible Research and Innovation into researchers’, developers’, users’ practices and policies, and finally offer mechanisms and tools that will support decision-making to challenges and opportunities related to digitation.

DESIRA overarching goal is fulfilled through 6 objectives. Each objective has specific requirements of data collection/generation, as reported in the following table.

1: to fill the socio-economic knowledge gaps on digitisation in agriculture, rural areas and forestry through the	Obj 1 will require the collection and elaboration of data, often as reports,
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development, dissemination and communication of a transdisciplinary Conceptual and Analytical Framework and a Taxonomy and Inventory of Digital Game Changers.	publications or multimedia, to better understand socio-economic gaps and needs, to use data in the applications we will develop, to analyse trends and provide recommendations, to develop the taxonomy of game changers.
2: to assess the past and current socio-economic impact of digitisation in relation to Sustainable Development Goals by carrying out, disseminating and communicating a participatory Socio-Economic Impact Assessment of digitisation based on an innovative assessment methodology.	Obj2 will require the production of a set of SDG-based indicators, elaborated from statistical available data at NUTS3 level and from interviews to key informants
3: to improve the capacity of rural communities to reflect on future risks and opportunities related to digitisation by co-creating, disseminating and communicating a set of rural digitisation scenarios, and by developing Use Cases and two Showcase technologies including a Virtual Farm Platform, adopting RRI-based value sensitive solutions.	Obj3 will elaborate and publish text data produced through interaction at level of Living Labs
4: to improve the capacity of rural communities to reap the opportunities offered by digitisation and to improve resilience to related hazards by identifying and assessing existing policy instruments, by developing a Policy Roadmap, and by promoting the embodiment of an Ethical Code into private and public innovation strategies.	Obj4 will elaborate and publish text and visual data produced through interaction at level of Living labs
5: to promote online interaction and learning – complementary to face-to-face interaction - among a wide range of stakeholders through a Virtual Research Environment, which will provide online tools for knowledge exchange and easy and open access to research findings.	In the fulfilment of Obj5, data will be generated through online activities. Moreover, data collected for other objectives will be made available through dedicated software
6: to increase the uptake of societal concerns in ICT-related policy and innovation, and to align digitisation scenarios with societal needs and expectations through an effective Exploitation, dissemination, communication and outreach strategy.	Obj6 will produce and distribute reports, scientific papers, easy to communicate short reports, and multimedia products

3.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

DESIRA is a complex project, based on a participatory approach. Its core activities will be based on the work of 20 living labs and a Rural Digitization Forum, so most of the collected data will be originated by the organized interaction with stakeholders. These data will be integrated by a) scientific literature; b) official statistical data; c) numeric data based on interviews to experts; d) text and image data available on the web; e) data collected through a survey. Table 1 shows a synthetic description of the data that will be used during the project. Annex 1 will provide a more detailed description.

Table 1 - Synthesis of data collected by work package

Dataset	Type	Origin	Format	Expected size	Availability	Utility
WP1 Survey on 900	Text data	Elaborated by consortium partners based	.xls		Open	Researchers, AKIS, general

digitization projects and tools		on interviews and websites				public
All WPs	Published papers	Journals and books	.pdf		Open	Researchers
WP2 EUROSTAT dataset NUTS3 level	Numeric data	Official statistical data	.xls		Open	Researchers
WP2 Digitisation index database	Numeric data	Indicators elaborated by the consortium on statistical data	.xls		Open	Researchers, AKIS
WP2 Socio-economic Sustainability Impact database	Numeric data	Indicators elaborated by the consortium based on mixed sources	.xls		Open	Researchers, AKIS
WP2, WP3 Minutes of the Living Labs workshops	Text data	Living Labs	.pdf		Open	Researchers, Living Lab participants
WP2 Interview transcripts	Text data	Trascription by the consortium on recorded interviews	.pdf		Open	Researchers
WP2 survey	Text/Numeric data	Data collected through a syrvey to a sample	.xls		Open after anonymization procedures	Researchers
WP6 Webinars	Multimedia data		n.a.		Open	Researchers, AKIS
WP6 digital stories	Multimedia data	Images taken by researchers and Living Lab participants	n.a.		Open	Researchers, AKIS, general public
WP6 Minutes of the RDF	Text data	Consortium	.pdf		Open	Members of the consortium
WP2 Online survey dataset	Numeric / text data	Questionnaire sent to DESIRA Living Labs components	.xls		Open	Researchers
WP5 Online forum data	Text data	Data generated through the VRE activity	.pdf		Restricted	Members of the consortium
WP5 VRE monitoring	Numeric data	Data usage statistics	.xls		Restricted	Members of the consortium
ALL WPs Working documents and Deliverables	Reports	Own elaboration	.pdf		Open	Researchers, AKIS, general public

Presentations to meetings, workshops, conferences	Presentation	Own elaboration	.pdf / ppt		Open	Researchers, AKIS, general public
Practice abstracts	Short document	Own elaboration	.xls		Open	Researchers, AKIS, general public
Policy briefs	Short document	Own elaboration	.pdf		Open	Researchers, AKIS, general public
Scientific articles	Scientific articles	Own elaboration	.pdf		Open	Researchers, AKIS

3.3 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

DESIRA will capitalize on already existing data and will integrate them with new data. Table below shows the main data on which DESIRA will capitalize

Wp1	Literature review Survey of 900 tools and projects based on project websites and other sources
WP2	Literature review EUROSTAT and national statistical data
WP3	Review of literature and data available at national level
WP4	Review of literature and data available at national level
WP5	Literature review at European and national level
WP6	Existing materials on the topic will be disseminated

For all available data, appropriate references to authors and institutions will be given.

4. FAIR data

4.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?

D4Science can activate a dedicated catalogue in the environment. This Catalogue will be based on CKAN technology, enriched with plenty of additional features. The DESIRA Catalogue can be configured to support publications per VRE and global, several metadata types, custom resource types, custom groups, etc.

For each type, the metadata format reported in the DMP will be defined.

Then, from the workspace authorised people will be able to publish a file (or all files included in a folder) by selecting the type and by filling in the required metadata.

A DOI will be assigned to final versions of each data item.

What naming conventions do you follow?

The general convention we will use is the following:

[WPx] [title] [year] [month] [verx] [.] ext

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

yes

Do you provide clear version numbers?

DESIRA uses a Virtual Research Environment with a workspace that automatically assigns a version number to the files of the workspace when a new file with the same name is uploaded. All versions are conserved in the VRE and accessible through a unique and persistent URI. Moreover, any object and any of its versions stored in the workspace can be published in the DESIRA Catalogue.

Data Items: specification of metadata

The following data items are foreseen to be created at this stage:

- Reports: metadata are included at the beginning of the same file.
- Database: metadata are included in a separate sheet of the same excel file of the database.
- Presentations: Metadata are included at the end of the same file.
- Multimedia data: Metadata are included at the end of the same file.
- Practice abstracts, Policy briefs: Metadata are included at the end of the same file.

Reports

All DESIRA reports will display the following information on their third page:

CALL	H2020-RUR-2018-2
WORK PROGRAMME	Topic SFS-29-2017 Socio-eco-economics - socio-economics in ecological approaches
Project ID	818194
Project web site	www.desira2020.eu
Document type	(deliverable, working document)
Title	
Authors	
Date of creation	
Status of the document	Draft / Final version
Version number	
Internal reviewers	
Keywords	
Coverage	

Moreover, the file will report this sentence:

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Database

Databases will be made available in .xlsx format. Metadata will follow the Dublin Core format (<https://www.dublincore.org/>).

Content	Intellectual Property	Instantiation
Title	Creator	Date
Subject	Publisher	Format
Description	Contributor	Identifier
	Rights	Language
Type		
Source		
Relation		
Coverage		

In the first sheet (metadata), the following metadata will be available (based on Dublin Core Format):

General information

CALL	H2020-RUR-2018-2
WORK PROGRAMME	Topic SFS-29-2017 Socio-eco-economics - socio-economics in ecological approaches
Project ID	818194
Project web site	www.desira2020.eu
Database type	Numeric, textual
Title	
Creator	
Contributors	
Publisher	
Date	
Format	
Status of the document	Draft / Final version
Draft version n.	
Identifier	

Each database will be provided with information about structure and content, as follows. In some cases, information on the quality of the data will be provided.

Information about database structure and content

Field Label	Description	Type (numeric, text, time, y/n)	Format

Presentations

General information

CALL	H2020-RUR-2018-2
WORK PROGRAMME	Topic SFS-29-2017 Socio-eco-economics - socio-economics in ecological approaches
Project ID	818194
Project web site	www.desira2020.eu
Document type	Presentation
Title	
Authors	
Status of the document	Draft / Final version
Draft version n.	
Where presented	Location, event
Date of presentation	
Keywords	

Multimedia

All multimedia products will have this metadata at the end of the file:

CALL	H2020-RUR-2018-2
WORK PROGRAMME	Topic SFS-29-2017 Socio-eco-economics - socio-economics in ecological approaches
Project ID	818194
Project web site	www.desira2020.eu
Document type	Video, Digital story,
Title	
Authors	
Status of the document	Draft / Final version
Draft version n.	
Keywords	
Link	
Credits	

5. Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

Most produced data will be openly available as the default, with the exception of the database of the user-generated content of the VREs, as this is internal communication with little relevance for outsiders. However, these data may be made available upon motivated request after anonymization.

How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?

All DESIRA data will be stored on the Zenodo repository after delivery to the REA. Before that moment, the data will be stored in the DESIRA VRE and accessible to all consortium members.

Zenodo assigns a DOI to all documents uploaded, and allows the storage of metadata.

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Most files will be accessible with general use software (word, excel, power point and their open versions). Inventory of game changers (WP5) will have a version accessible via web, and a specific open access software will be created. The DESIRA VRE offers space to store data also to the applications and not only to the humans. This is possible by using the Application token that is available for all environments and by exploiting the APIs that we provide.

Next versions of the DMP will be more specific for other types of data.

Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

See above

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.

All DESIRA data will be stored on the Zenodo repository after delivery to the REA. Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

Yes

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?

Restriction is foreseen only for data generated by the internal social tool used by researchers within the VRE. They will be released upon approval of the data producers.

Is there a need for a data access committee?

NO

Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine readable license)? How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Conditions for access are specified in the annex.

6. Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

All metadata will refer to the Dublin Core. Moreover, we will make our metadata available following the OAI-PMH standard. OAI-PMH will come for free if the project decides to exploit the DESIRA Catalogue service provided by D4Science.

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

These are community specific. A partial list of them should be included.

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

Next version of the DMP will address this aspect

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Next version of the DMP will address this aspect

7. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

DESIRA reports will be licensed under Creative commons license. Specifications are made in the annex I

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

In general, data produced in the project will be made openly available as soon as the related deliverables are uploaded in the Project Portal. Specific arrangements are specified in Annex I.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

yes

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable? Are data quality assurance processes described?

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address:

8. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?

Zenodo will be the main open access repository selected to make data FAIR. However, some papers will be selected to be published under the 'golden' option.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

10000 EUR have been allocated to open access

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Project coordinator

Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?

Already in the grant agreement.

9. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

Data are collected and stored in the DESIRA workspace.

This repository is secured with Transport Level Security (TLS) that provides communications security over the computer network. It ensures privacy and data integrity between two communicating computer applications. In particular, any connections between a client (e.g., a web browser) and the DESIRA workspace have the following properties:

- The connection is *private* (or *secure*) thanks to the adoption of the symmetric cryptography to encrypt the data transmitted. The keys for this symmetric encryption are generated uniquely for each connection and are based on a shared secret negotiated at the start of the session. The server and client negotiate the details of which encryption algorithm and cryptographic keys to use before the first byte of data is transmitted. The negotiation of a shared secret is both secure (the negotiated secret is unavailable to eavesdroppers and cannot be obtained, even by an attacker who places themselves in the middle of the connection) and reliable (no attacker can modify the communications during the negotiation without being detected);
- The identity of the communicating parties can be *authenticated* using public-key cryptography. This authentication can be made optional at client side, but is ensured at the server side;
- The connection ensures *integrity* because each message transmitted includes a message integrity check using a message authentication code to prevent undetected loss or alteration of the data during transmission;
- The connection ensures forward secrecy, ensuring that any future disclosure of encryption keys cannot be used to decrypt any TLS communications recorded in the past.

A backup and recovery strategy has been put in place to protect about data loss incidents that can take a variety of forms, but when it comes to a workspace technology, they generally fall into two categories: catastrophic failure and human error. Even if catastrophic failure includes natural disasters and any other scenario that permanently destroy all the server nodes most of the issues are generated by human error. Humans introduce application bugs or accidentally delete data. A bad code release that corrupts some or all of the production data is an unfortunate but common example. In the case of human error, the errors introduced will propagate automatically to the replicas, often within seconds.

The DESIRA workspace provides continuous, online backup for data as a fully managed service. The service streams encrypted and compressed *oplog* data to a dedicated server so that a continuous backup is activated. By default, the DESIRA workspace takes snapshots every 6 hours and oplog data is retained for 24 hours.

Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

yes

10. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

As reported in the Grant Agreement, the main ethical issues for DESIRA concerns Research involving Human beings and the Protection of Personal Data. All the internal procedures needed to assure the compliance with the requirements have been so far developed in Deliverable 8.1 "H - requirement No. 1" and in Deliverable 7.3 "Ethical Guidelines".

These two Deliverables further detail the procedures of information of research participants already included in the Grant Agreement, to guarantee that prior to the collection of any data, participants will be informed on the collection, processing and use of data provided and that contact persons of the Consortium will ensure that they give the consent (D. 8.1). Research activities interested by ethics requirements in each Work Package are detailed in Deliverable 7.3, together with a list of actions to be taken in order to guarantee the compliance.

D.7.3 reports the information sheet and the informed consent statement, which includes details about: data collection, data use, data analysis, data storage and long term preservation, data anonymisation and the right to withdraw the participation.

Deliverable 8.2 "POPD – Requirement N.2", due at month 12 of the Project, will report the confirmation of the appointment of a Data Protection Officer by the beneficiaries, as well as the organisational measures.

11. Other issues

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?

12. Further support in developing your DMP

The Research Data Alliance provides a [Metadata Standards Directory](#) that can be searched for discipline-specific standards and associated tools.

The [EUDAT B2SHARE](#) tool includes a built-in license wizard that facilitates the selection of an adequate license for research data.

Useful listings of repositories include:

- [Registry of Research Data Repositories](#)
- Some repositories like [Zenodo](#), an OpenAIRE and CERN collaboration), allow researchers to deposit both publications and data, while providing tools to link them.
- Other useful tools include [DMP online](#) and platforms for making individual scientific observations available such as [ScienceMatters](#).

ANNEX 1 - List of data items planned in the DESIRA project

Work Package n.	Title of document/database	Type	Origin of data	Format	Availability	Target users	Licence (*)
WP1	Survey on DGCs	Text database	online survey	.csv .pdf .html .doc	open after anonymization	consortium	CC BY CC
WP1	Interviews	Text files	experts' interviews	.pdf	open after embargo	consortium	BYS A
WP1	Report on DGCs	Published papers	online survey, public reports, meetings	.pdf	open	researchers	CC0
WP1	Deliverables	Report files	online survey, public reports, meetings, experts' interviews, scientific literature	.pdf	open after embargo	researchers	CC BY
WP2	Dataset of Rural Digitization Index at NUTS3 level	Numeric database	eurostat	xlsx	1 year after completion of the project	Researchers	CC0
WP2	Transcripts of interviews to key informants	Text files	own production	.docx	restricted	DESIRA consortium	CC0
WP2	Dataset of SESI indicators	Text files	own production	.docx	open	all DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP2	Minutes of workshop	Text files	Own production	.docx	open after anonymization	all DESIRA target groups	CC0

WP2	Dataset of survey to LL stakeholders	Numerical database	Own production	.xlsx	1 year after completion of the project	all DESIRA target groups	CCO
WP2	Living Labs NEI reports	Report files	Own production	.docx	1 year after completion of the project	all DESIRA target groups	CCO
WP3	Comparative scenario report	Report files	Synthesis of scenario development from the 20 Living Labs	.pdf	open after anonymization	Researchers/Policy-makers	CC BY
WP3	Policy briefs	Report files	Researcher	.pdf	open	Researchers/Policy-makers	CC BY
WP3	Use case report and showcase Technology report	Report files	Researcher analysis	.pdf	open	researchers	CC BY
WP3	Practice abstracts	Others Multimedia	Researcher summaries	.xlsx	open	Public	BY
WP3	Digital stories	Media files	Output from scenario workshops	mp4, mov, jpeg	open after anonymization	Public	CCO
WP3	Guidelines to socio-economic assessment	Report files	Own production	.docx	2 year after completion of the project	all DESIRA target groups	CCO
WP4	National Policy Reports	Report files	Researchers collection	.docx	Open	Researchers/Policy-makers	CC BY
WP4	Policy Roadmap	Report files	National Policy Reports	.docx	Open	Researchers/Policy-makers	CC BY
WP4	Policy Analysis	Published papers	Policy Roadmap	.docx	Open	Researchers/Policy-makers	CCO
WP4	Minutes of policy auditions	Text files	Ad hoc meetings	.docx	open after anonymization	Researchers	CC BY

WP6	Audio content/Artlist	Multimedia	https://artlist.io/	mp3	Unlimited	All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Audio content/Istock	Multimedia	www.istockphoto.com	mp3		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Audio content/Shutterstock	Multimedia	www.shutterstock.com	mp3		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Audio content/Dreamstime	Multimedia	www.dreamstime.com	mp3		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Audio content/123rf	Multimedia	https://www.123rf.com	mp3		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Audio content/DESIRA audio material (podcasts)	Multimedia	Own production	mp3	3 years after completion of the project	All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Graphic content (photos, pictures)/European Commission - Audiovisual Service	Multimedia	https://audiovisual.ec.europa.eu	png, jpeg, tif, gif		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Graphic content (photos, pictures)/Pxhere	Multimedia	https://pxhere.com/	png, jpeg, tif, gif	Unlimited	All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Graphic content (photos, pictures)/Stock Snap	Multimedia	https://stocksnap.io/	png, jpeg, tif, gif	Unlimited	All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Graphic content (photos, pictures)/Unsplash	Multimedia	https://unsplash.com/	png, jpeg, tif, gif	Unlimited	All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Graphic content (photos, pictures)/Life of pix	Multimedia	https://www.lifeofpix.com/	png, jpeg, tif, gif	Unlimited	All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Graphic content (photos,	Multimedia	Own production	ai, eps,	3 years after	All DESIRA	CC0

	pictures)/DESIRA graphic material	edia		png, jpeg, tif, gif	completion of the project	target groups	
WP6	Graphic content (photos, pictures)/Pixabay	Multimedia	pixabay.com	png, jpeg, tif, gif	Unlimited	All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Graphic content (photos, pictures)/Adobe stock	Multimedia	stock.adobe.com	png, jpeg, tif, gif		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Graphic content (photos, pictures)/iStock	Multimedia	www.istockphoto.com	png, jpeg, tif, gif		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Graphic content (photos, pictures)/Pexels	Multimedia	www.pexels.com	png, jpeg, tif, gif	Unlimited	All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Graphic content (photos, pictures)/Shutterstock	Multimedia	www.shutterstock.com	png, jpeg, tif, gif		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Graphic content (photos, pictures)/123rf	Multimedia	https://www.123rf.com	png, jpeg, tif, gif		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Graphic content (photos, pictures)/Dreams Time	Multimedia	www.dreamstime.com	png, jpeg, tif, gif		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Statistics/Mailchimp	Numerical data	Target audience			DESIRA WP6 leader	Private
WP6	Personal data/Mailchimp	Text data	Target audience	xlsx	3 years after completion of the project	DESIRA WP6 leader	Private
WP6	Video content/European Commission - Audiovisual Service	Multimedia	https://audiovisual.ec.europa.eu	mp4		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Video content/DESIRA video production (video interviews,	Multimedia	Own production	avi, mp4	3 years after completion of	All DESIRA target	CC0

webinars, digital stories)					the project	groups	
WP6	Video content/Pixabay	Multimedia	pixabay.com	mp4	Unlimited	All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Video content/Adobe stock	Multimedia	stock.adobe.com	mp4		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Video content/iStock	Multimedia	www.istockphoto.com	mp4		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Video content/Pexels	Multimedia	www.pexels.com	mp4	Unlimited	All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Video content/123rf	Multimedia	https://www.123rf.com	mp4		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Video content/Dreams Time	Multimedia	www.dreamstime.com	mp4		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Video content/Shutterstock	Multimedia	www.shutterstock.com	mp4		All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Website/Statistics Google Analytics	Numerical data	https://analytics.google.com/analytics/web/provision/?authuser=0#/provision	pdf, xlsx	3 years after completion of the project	DESIRA consortium	Private
WP6	Website/Forum registrants	Text data	www.desira2020.eu	pdf, html	3 years after completion of the project	DESIRA WP6 leader	Private
WP6	Website/Youtube	Multimedia	www.youtube.com	mp4	3 years after completion of the project	All DESIRA target groups	CC0
WP6	Website/Editorial production	Text files	Own production	pdf		All DESIRA target groups	CC0

